

LINGUACULTURAL APPROACH TO AUDIOVISUAL TRANSLATION

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The film industry is considered one of the dominant forms of culture in the modern age. Going beyond art, it has inevitably become a part of people's lives, having a considerable impact on the formation of their language, lifestyle, and even values. In this regard, audiovisual translation is undoubtedly the most common type of translation oriented towards a huge market and audience. However, it causes problems for a translator to overcome both linguistic and extralinguistic barriers while translating audiovisual products. Since there is a wide range of platforms for watching films and television series of different genres, it is not relevant to deal with standard forms and stereotyped storylines. Screenwriters, producers, and directors have to look for new ways of interacting with an intended audience that will make them hooked on watching the next franchises. The old genre of television series is no exception to that popular trend. The concept of television series has been given a new interpretation. It is not merely a set of television episodes shown at certain time intervals. Over the past few years, the quality and quantity of television series produced in the world have significantly increased. In terms of the art of acting, directing, and camerawork, some series can be highly competitive with wide-screen blockbusters and are no longer perceived as soap operas. Moreover, many viewers consider series as an integral part of their lives, watching their favorite episodes several times.

It should be pointed out that new fantasy films and television series have become extremely popular with the audience of all ages and categories. One example is an American fantasy television series the "Game of Thrones", released in 2011-2019 and quickly excited the curiosity of millions of people around the world. It claims to be a cult television series and has already been translated into more than 45 languages. Since a fantasy genre implies the creation of a fictional world, it is necessary to identify how professional translators cope with various culture-specific elements of the original.

Most of the times different cultural societies clash in film translation by making it too hard for translators to render the original meaning. An inadequate

communicative effect involves such problems as misperception of the target text, unequal emotions, loss of emotional and aesthetic perception. In this regard, the translator should take into account the difference between the linguistic environments of both source and target recipients following different cultural subtexts and a set of knowledge. If the difference causes misunderstanding, the translator should try to compensate it by making necessary changes to the translation.

In modern linguistic and cultural studies, special attention is paid to the linguacultural approach to the study of national realia, denoting ethno-specific concepts of a particular country, nation, and historical epoch. At the same time, many researchers such as Baker and Ritva note that there are no clear criteria for determining these extralinguistic elements either in communication theory or in translation studies. Moreover, this foreign vocabulary layer is called differently in different scientific works: non-equivalent vocabulary, exotic vocabulary or exoticisms, culture-bound vocabulary, barbarisms, localisms, gaps or lacunas, linguoculturemes. It should be noted that all these terms are similar in some way since they denote objects and phenomena with national, local, or historical coloring that do not have correspondences or equivalents in the target language. However, the abovementioned terms cannot be considered synonymous or interchangeable, as they denote slightly different concepts. Thus, realia are the words and phrases naming objects existing in the life and culture of one nation and absent in another. Given that the original culture-specific units are unknown to most target language speakers, they do not have exact equivalents in the target language. In our research, the analysis of linguacultural peculiarities of translating the fantasy television series “Game of Thrones” is based on this interpretation of realia since it seems to be the most precise and appropriate. While translating fantasy television series from English into Russian, it is difficult to choose the method of transferring the concept of a nonexistent world to a viewer from the real world on its certain cultural, social, and historical development. Over the last several decades, realia-related matters have been actively discussed in the field of translation studies, intercultural communication, theory of literature, linguistic and cultural studies. It is not a new linguistic problem. According to Baker “there are no such things as untranslatable words, i.e., any words can be translated at least descriptively”. Therefore, the question is not whether it is possible or impossible to translate realia, but what methods of translation should be applied

According to scholars as Anderman and Jorge Diaz Cintaz, engaged in audiovisual translation problems, the term 'subtitling' can be defined as an abridged translation of the film dialogues reflecting their main content and presenting the visual sequence of the original film in the form of a printed text, usually given at the bottom of the screen. Voice-over translation is another type of audiovisual conversion of the film dialogue from one language into another. The script is first translated, then recorded by a native-speaking voice-over translator. It is vital for a voice talent to have an appropriate voice accent, articulation, and interpretation to appeal to the target audience. The process of audiovisual translation goes hand in hand with cultural phenomena. The translator's task is to overcome the cultural distance between the source and target languages by applying basic methods of adapting original culture-specific elements in translation. If the meaning of these nonequivalent units is conveyed properly, it will provide an adequate perception of the author's intention by the target audience. The translator is a guide for the television viewers as well as a part of their culture. Consequently, a translation for strangers will certainly result in a loss of adequacy. On the one hand, the adaptation of the film dialogue includes conveying the meaning of the characters' statements. On the other hand, it serves to preserve the stylistic features of dialogues and achieve a pragmatic effect.

The aim of the research is achieved by implementing the linguacultural approach to audiovisual translation along with the traditional research methods. The linguacultural approach was used to find the connection between language and culture. The descriptive analysis is applied to characterize culture-specific elements of audiovisual content, whereas the comparative analysis provides further insight into the nature of cultural gaps between the source and target languages. The statistical analysis allows revealing the most common modes and principles of adapting audiovisual materials in translation. The analysis serves to improve the process of audiovisual translation specifying new requirements for the translator's professional competences. It should be emphasized that the linguacultural peculiarities of audiovisual translation are not only one of the most complex translation aspects but also one of the most interesting and informative issues. The process of audiovisual translation requires a special linguacultural approach that can provide an adequate perception of the audiovisual content by the target audience. It should be pointed out that in the film industry, the timeline and linguistic features have a significant effect on the translator's work. Taking into account this fact, the translator should not only

possess standard translation skills but pay attention to the role of the film dialogue and the peculiar features of the main characters' colloquial speech. In this case, it will be possible to adapt the original audiovisual text to the target audience. The linguacultural aspect of audiovisual translation usually involves the following difficulties:

–the presence of audiovisual channels of perception interacting and complementing each other; –the compliance of the translation to the image on the screen; –the inability of the translator to interpret concepts unknown for the new target audience; –the dominance of the principle of ensuring a pragmatic effect.

It should be concluded that the translator does not play a major role in audiovisual translation. The result of the translation will also depend on the work of editors and directors. Despite the fact that the translator has provided an adequate translation, after synchronizing the text with audio and video sequence, the degree of adequacy may decrease. Hence, when analyzing the translation of a script, the responsibility for its adequacy and equivalence rests not only with the translator. Besides, the main disadvantages of dubbing are poor-quality translation and misinterpretation of the content of the text. That's why the viewers who watch films in the original, often blame the translators for the deviations found in the target audiovisual text, being unaware of the fact that the translator takes little part in the process of synchronizing the text. Summing up the main ideas of the article, we have compiled the following essential guidelines for overcoming linguacultural barriers in audiovisual translation:

1. depending on the genre, social, and age orientation of the audiovisual product, there is a tendency to use certain vocabulary which must be properly adapted for the target audience. The translator needs to possess a bicultural competence which implies a deep background knowledge in both source and target cultures;
2. unlike translation of a literary work, audiovisual translation requires the target text to be synchronized and consistent with the timeline and articulation of actors. Therefore, the translator has to shorten the original text so that it can follow the audio and video sequence on the screen;
3. first and foremost, a television series is a play of actors accompanied by a certain musical scale. In this regard, the translator's task is to convey all peculiarities of the original speeches without changing the series director's idea;
4. discrepancies between the source and target linguacultural aspects based on a different system of values and concepts may cause inevitable losses in the

perception of the text by the target receptor. That's why the translator usually chooses between two basic strategies of foreignization and domestication. The first one is presumed to convey the national features of the source culture. The second one is expected to adapt the text so that it could be easily understood by the target audience;

5. the translator should bear in mind that the success of a film or television series depends on its spectacularity and visual appeal rather than on its equivalence to the original.

Literature review:

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